

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 14th December 2022

Accepted: 24th December 2022

Online: 25th December 2022

KEY WORDS

**PROBLEMS IN THE CONSTRUCTION OF LOW-STORY
RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS**

¹Eshmuratov Abilqosim Egamberdiyevich

Senior lecturer at Samarkand State University of Architecture and
Construction,

²Eshmuratov Orif Abilqosimovich.

Teacher, Samarkand State University of Architecture and Construction

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7482891>

ABSTRACT

In this article, changes in materials lead to erosion, suffocation, building collapse, electrochemical, chemical, physical, physico-chemical and biological corrosion due to various conditions used in building materials. The effects of various types of aggressive substances in water in solid, liquid, and gaseous states increase on the destruction of construction structures.

Today's in the day In our republic under construction less layered residence and public buildings in construction in the sokol part of the buildings being used makeup from materials use during, it is known one time from the past after exploitation during meeting some one to shortcomings stopping I want to pass.

External obstacle to constructions chemical or physicist effects because of external effect condition because of construction of

materials own from himself decay condition happened gives Ush this to the outside in fact corrosion take will come and another from the processes, in the material changes because of erosion, suffosis, building to decay take will come Construction in materials different used situations because of electrochemical, chemical, physical, physico-chemical and biological to corrosions take will come

if construction in materials of the composition to change take coming factors physical and chemical to decay take will come That's why for construction in materials corrosion this attention It is a non- falling process and materials from the characteristics to change and destruction from materials and construction as a result

chemical or physical and chemical or biological in effects to changes take will come

Construction in materials corrosion because of in decay their weight, section, strength or from many a lot characteristics deterioration and construction to materials quality indicators to change take will come

CHANGING SITUATIONS TODAY

This buildings the wall and foundation parts in constructions to the pores atmosphere and grunts effect as a result hydration come it turns out that while construction of constructions to decay water all kinds of contents kind of aggressive substances solid, liquid, gas in the situation effects increased goes Everyone time buildings are different construction and materials in the pores water accumulation increased goes Construction materials in the composition

water salts external external to the part looking come out starts This on surfaces dry external layer in construction appear to be building external Apparently, it is known one at times while capital repair of work take to go take will come

Permission done humidity percentage architectural exploitation conditions brick at a rate of $1.5 \div 3 \%$ (max condition 4.5%), concrete walls for $8 \div 12 \%$ (max condition 17 %) permit will be done .

Construction in constructions hydrations reason and come output the following reasons because of come output :

- construction
- household
- from the atmosphere
- from grunts

Construction humidity construction constructions in preparation , transportation, installation, restoration brick dial during appear It will be small elemental in construction construction humidity big in size exploitation in the process humidity percentage permission from being done increased goes 1 m³ up to 200 l on my skin water to be can Natural in case this the process to see long in term wet amount reach can Household humidity rooms inside people by neglect because of fruit will be Atmosphere humidity in the atmosphere of moisture change the wind under the influence of of rain effect external on surfaces don't miss it harvest to

be, of temperature changes in roof coverings and etc

Soil moisture of the building land bottom in parts humidity in tolalas construction of materials cracks and damaged in places appear will be Construction in materials capillaries diametrically how much small if so, they have it hydration quantity that's all high will be

In soil moisture basically them land under waters contained of minerals composition, quantity depends without 1 liter water contained minerals to the amount depends without is studied. That's why for buildings in the sokol part of hydration come exit reasons, amount, size and another the facts ok consider as options and winter in season building external obstacle constructions uncomfortable ob the air effect because of come coming out of circumstances prevention to get from the ground We believe that it will give.

References:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev " In 2017-2021 village in places updated exemplary projects according to cheap houses on the construction program decision Tashkent, October 21, 2016 .
2. QMQ 2.01.04-18 - « Construction heat technique ". Tashkent: 2018.
3. ESTulakov . of buildings energy efficiency Engineering: Education manual - SamDU: 2020 - 240 p.
4. V.S Abrashitov Technical operation and inspection of building structures. Tutorial. – M.: ASV, 2005.
5. Тулаков Э.С., Бўронов Х., Матёқубов Б.П., Абдуллаева С. А.. Кам қаватли турар-жой бинолари ертўла деворларининг иссиқлик изоляция қатлами қалинлигини ҳисоблаш. //Ме'morchilik va qurilish muammolari Проблемы архитектуры и строительства.Samarqand 2020. №2. -С.41-45.
6. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Energy Efficient Building Materials for External Walls of Residential Buildings Physical Properties of Heat. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 1–11. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/67>
7. Тулаков Э.С., Матёқубов Б.П.. Thermal Insulation Of The Foundation Walls Of Buildings And Calculation Of Its Thickness. THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY (TAJET) SJIF-5.705 DOI-10.37547/tajet Volume 3 Issue 04, 2021 ISSN 2689-0984 The USA Journals, USA www.usajournalshub.com/index.php/tajet -C.70-78

8. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Analysis of Underground Projects of Energy-Efficient Residential Buildings. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 9, 12–18. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/68>
9. Inatillayevich, G.O. and Pulatovich, M.B. 2021. Analysis of Underground Projects of Energy Efficient Low-Rise Residential Buildings Built on Highly Flooded Soils. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 4, 9 (Sep. 2021), 96-102. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v4i9.2156>.
10. Pulatovich, M. B. ., & Inatillayevich, G. O. . (2021). Laboratory Experimental Studies on the Properties of Highly Sedimentary Lyos Soils when their Moisture Changes Over Time. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 8, 91-98. Retrieved from <http://ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/119>
11. Pulatovich, M. B. ., & Shodiyev, K. . (2021). Thermal Insulation of Basement Walls of Low-Rise Residential Buildings and Calculation of its Thickness. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 9, 19–27. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/69>
12. Матёкубов, Бобур Пўлатович, and Сарвара Музаффаровна Саидмуродова. "КАМ СУВ ТАЛАБЧАН БОҒЛОВЧИ АСОСИДАГИ ВЕРМИКУЛИТЛИ ЕНГИЛ БЕТОНЛАР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ." *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*. Vol. 1. No. 15. 2022.
13. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Energy Efficient Building Materials for External Walls of Residential Buildings Physical Properties of Heat. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 9, 1–11. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/67>
14. Khayitov, Maruf Bolikulovich. "THERMAL INSULATION MATERIALS: ADVANTAGES AND PRODUCTION." *Theoretical & Applied Science* 1 (2021): 375-378.
15. Тулаков Э.С., Инояттов Д., Курбонов А.С., Матёкубов Б.П.. Бинолар-нинг ертўла деворларини иссиқлик изоляциялаш ва унинг қалинлигини ҳисоблаш. //Ме'morchilik va qurilish muammolari Проблемы архитектуры и строительства.Samarqand 2020. №4.(2-қисм) -С.29-32.
16. Матёкубов, Б. П., & Саидмуродова, С. М. (2022). КАМ СУВ ТАЛАБЧАН БОҒЛОВЧИ АСОСИДАГИ ВЕРМИКУЛИТЛИ ЕНГИЛ БЕТОНЛАР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ. *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES*, 1(15), 103–109. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/cf/article/view/319>
17. Inatillayevich G. O., Pulatovich M. B. Analysis of Underground Projects of Energy Efficient Low-Rise Residential Buildings Built on Highly Flooded Soils <https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v4i9>. – Т. 2156.
18. Matyokubov , B. P., & Saidmuradova, S. M. (2022). METHODS FOR INVESTIGATION OF THERMOPHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF UNDERGROUND EXTERNAL BARRIER STRUCTURES OF BUILDINGS. *RESEARCH AND EDUCATION*, 1(5), 49–58. Retrieved from <http://researchedu.org/index.php/re/article/view/364>
19. Акбарали У., и Дилноза К. (2022). Национальная культура архитектуры здания банкетного зала и принципы ее формирования. *Международный журнал культуры и*

- современности, 22, 31-40. Извлечено из
<https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/427>
20. Fazilov Farhod, & Mamadaliyev Xayrulla. (2022). THREE-LAYER REINFORCED CONCRETE WALL PANELS FROM LIGHT AND HEAVY CONCRETE FOR CIVIL BUILDINGS. World Bulletin of Management and Law, 17, 24-28. Retrieved from <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbml/article/view/1777>
21. Editor Journals and Conferences. (2022, November 22). HEAT-SHIELDING QUALITIES AND METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE HEAT-SHIELDING QUALITIES OF WINDOW BLOCKS AND THEIR JUNCTION NODE WITH WALLS. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/CB57D>
22. Mamadaliev, K., & Sirozhiddinov, S. (2021). Ways to use energy-efficient wall structures in residential buildings. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 81-85. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/83>